

Naturally Occurring Coumarino-lignoids

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The spectral studies on coumarino-lignoids reported in the literature have been discussed. All the compounds that have been isolated from various plant species have been enlisted. The structures of coumarino-lignoids and their biomimetic synthesis from C₆-C₃-C₆ units have been presented.

Coumarino-lignoids are relatively new and rare group of natural products arising from C₆, C₃, C₆ units. In these molecules a coumarin moiety is linked with a phenyl propanoid unit through a 1,4-dioxan bridge.

The coumarino-lignoids were first isolated from the seeds of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. (Fam. : Capparidaceae) by Ray and coworkers¹⁻⁷ and these were designated as cleomiscosin A (1) and cleomiscosin B (2). Ray and his colleagues established the structure of this regioisomeric pair from spectral analyses and chemical reactions. The compounds were later synthesised by Cordell and his research group⁸ by oxidative coupling of the coumarin, fraxetin (15) with coniferyl alcohol (16).

Till to-date only fourteen coumarino-lignoids have been isolated from natural sources and have been found to be distributed in plant species belonging to eight families Capparidaceae, Simaroubaceae, Sapindaceae, Thymelaeaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Burseraceae, Aceraceae and Asclepiadaceae. The list of coumarino-lignoids along with their natural sources is given in Table 1.

Since no review on the coumarino-lignoids is available it was thought pertinent to compile the literature on this subject.

These compounds exhibit both linear and a

TABLE 1—COUMARINO-LIGNOIDS ISOLATED SO FAR FROM
NATURAL SOURCE

Compd. no.	Compd.	Source	Ref.
1	Cleomiscosin A	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> Linn. Fm. Capparidaceae <i>Smaba multiflora</i> A. Juss <i>S. soulameoides</i> (Gray) Fm. Simaroubaceae <i>Matayba arborescens</i> Radlk Fm. Sapindaceae <i>Aeseulus trubinata</i> Fm. Sapindaceae	1-7 9
2	Cleomiscosin B	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> Linn. <i>Acer saccharum</i> Marsh Fm. Aceraceae	6,7
3	Cleomiscosin C	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> Linn.	6,7
4	Cleomiscosin D	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> Linn.	10
5	Daphneticin	<i>Daphne tangutica</i> Maxim Fm. Thymelaeaceae	11
6	Compound B	<i>Jatropha glandulifera</i> Roxb. Fm. Euphorbiaceae	12
7	Propacin	<i>Protium opacum</i> Swart Fm. Burseraceae	13
8	Aquillochin	<i>Aquilaria agallocha</i> Roxb. Fm. Thymelaeaceae	14
9	Moluccanin	<i>Aleurites moluccana</i> (Linn.) Fm. Euphorbiaceae	15
10	Hemidesminine	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> R.Br. Fm. Asclepiadaceae	16
11	Hemidesmin 1	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> R.Br. Fm. Asclepiadaceae	17
12	Hemidesmin 2	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> R.Br. Fm. Asclepiadaceae	17
13	Aleuritin	<i>Aleurites fordii</i> Hemsl Fm. Euphorbiaceae	18
14	Flacourtin	<i>Flacourtia sepiaria</i> Roxb. Fm. Flacourtiaceae	19

angular structures. Moluccanin and hemidesminine have linear structures in which 1,4-dioxan bridge is formed involving the C-6 and C-7 positions of the coumarin nucleus whereas the angular compounds involve the linkage with C-7 and C-8. Excepting moluccanin and hemidesminine all the coumarino-lignoids have angular structures. Moreover, among all the coumarino-lignoids, hemidesminine (10) is the only compound which contains C₆-C₅ unit instead of C₆-C₃ to form the dioxan bridge¹⁶.

The structures of coumarino-lignoids were settled from spectral analyses (uv, ir, ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr and mass spectra) (Tables 2-5). 1,4-Dioxan bridge in these compounds is stable but can be cleaved with pyridine hydrochloride at elevated temperature. The latter provided an elegant method to ascertain the position of the linkage of the coumarin moiety. Mass spectrometry proved successful in structure elucidation of these compounds. It has been possible to establish the correct structure of hemidesminine (10) from the characteristic ion fragments *a*, *b* and *c*

in its mass spectrum. From an examination of similar ion species generated during the electron impact of other coumarino-lignoids it was possible to ascertain their structures. However, the problem arises in determining the positions of the substituents in coumarin unit and the methylol group in the 1,4-dioxan unit. These difficulties were encountered particularly in propacin (7) and aleuritin (13). In such cases hetero-decoupling experiments in conjunction with NOE effect¹⁸ have proved useful in establishing the correct structure as was evidenced in case of aleuritin (13) (Tables 6 and 7). Low power hetero-

decoupling was more effective for this purpose. Irradiation of 7'-H at δ 5.01 results in considerable sharpening of the C-6 signal at δ 128.90. Hence aleuritin can be represented as 13. The coupling constant of 7.66 Hz between 7'-H and 8'-H indicates the *trans*-orientation of the phenyl and methylol groups.

TABLE 2-NATURALLY OCCURRING COUMARINO-LIGNOIDS AND THEIR SPECTRAL DATA

Cleomiscosin A (1)

C₂₀H₁₈O₈ (*M*⁺ 386.0992), m.p. 247° (MeOH : EtOAc), [α]_D ± 0°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 288sh (5 661), 327 (10 550) nm [figure in parenthesis indicates ε/logε]; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 500, 1 720, 1 620, 1 580 cm⁻¹; MS (*M*⁺ 386, 52), 368 (18), 354 (14), 249 (18), 208 (38), 180 (94), 162 (20), 151 (10), 137 (100), 124 (54) [figure in parenthesis indicates rel. int.%]; ¹H nmr (C₅D₅N); δ ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) data in Table 3.

Source : *Cleome viscosa* Linn., *Simaba multiflora* A. Juss., *Matayba arborescens* Radlk.

Cleomiscosin B (2)

C₂₀H₁₈O₈ (*M*⁺ 386.1014), m.p. 274° (MeOH : EtOAc), [α]_D ± 0°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 285, 328 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 510, 1 720, 1 610, 1 560 cm⁻¹; MS (*M*⁺ 386, 48), 368 (2), 208 (5), 180 (100), 137 (85), 124 (48); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃), ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) data in Table 3.

Source : *Cleome viscosa* Linn., *Acer saccharum* Marsh.

Cleomiscosin C (3)

C₂₁H₂₀O₉ (*M*⁺ 416), m.p. 255° (MeOH : EtOAc), [α]_D ± 0°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 232sh (25 600), 280sh (4 160), 322 (12 160) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 420, 1 720, 1 685 cm⁻¹; MS 416 (*M*⁺, 7) 249 (5), 210 (56), 208 (45), 193 (21), 180 (34), 167 (100), 149 (50), 137

Table-2 (contd.)

(76), 109 (50), 91 (49), 79 (78); ^1H nmr ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$); ^{13}C nmr ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$) data in Table 3.

Source : *Cleome viscosa* Linn.

Cleomiscosin D (4)

$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_9$ (M^+ 416), m.p. 243–46° (MeOH : EtOAc); λ_{max} (EtOH) 214 (4.38), 232 (3.97), 325 (3.58) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 420, 1 710, 1 690 cm^{-1} ; MS 416 (M^+ , 19), 398 (14), 384 (19), 210 (100), 208 (27), 192 (13), 182 (31), 167 (68), 154 (25), 149 (32), 121 (16), 91 (15), 79 (19); ^1H nmr ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$); ^{13}C nmr ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$) data in Table 3.

Source : *Cleome viscosa* Linn.

Daphneticin (5)

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 386), m.p. 235–38°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} \pm 0^\circ$; λ_{max} (MeOH) 242 (9 170), 260 (8 892), 317 (11 230) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 480, 3 210, 1 730, 1 610, 1 570, 1 450, 1 340, 1 270, 1 115, 1 055, 835 cm^{-1} ; MS 386 (M^+ , 6), 354 (9), 311 (5), 210 (50), 178 (100), 167 (60), 150 (68); ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6); ^{13}C nmr ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$) data in Table 4.

Source : *Daphne tangutica* Maxim.

Compound B (6)

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ (M^+ 370), m.p. 245–48°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -56^\circ$; λ_{max} (MeOH) 257,

Table-2 (contd.)

334 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 380, 1 705, 1 610, 1 570, 1 500, 1 380, 1 035 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6).

Source : *Jatropha glandulifera* Roxb.

Propacin (7)

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ (M^+ , 370), m.p. 226–28° (CHCl₃-MeOH); λ_{max} (MeOH) 231 (33 000), 257 (inf 4 650), 286 (7 800), 323 (13 950) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 710, 1 615, 1 565, 1 450, 1 290, 1 145, 1 050, 840 cm^{-1} ; MS 370 (M^+ , -40), 327 (10), 233 (30), 164 (100); ^1H nmr (CDCl₃).

Source : *Protium opacum* Swart.

Aquillochin (8)

$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_9$ (M^+ 416.1129), m.p. 220° (MeOH); λ_{max} (MeOH) 326 (3.68) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 920, 1 715, 1 620, 1 610, 1 564, 1 420, 1 418, 1 316, 1 350, 1 118, 1 010 and 840 cm^{-1} ; MS (416.1129, 25), 398 (5), 249 (12.8), 219 (11.4), 210 (100), 208 (52.8), 193 (21.4), 182 (44.4), 167 (66.4), 154 (26.1), 137 (17.1), 121 (13.5), 107 (11.4), 91 (12.1), 79 (25.7); ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6). Source : *Aquilaria agallocha* Roxb.

Moluccanin (9)

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 386.0997), m.p. 220° (Me₂CO : MeOH), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} \pm$

Table-2 (contd.)

Table-2 (contd.)

Hemidesmin-2 (12)

0° ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 260, 295, 340 nm; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 520, 1 710 cm^{-1} , MS 386.0997 (M^+ 100), 355 (4.02), 354 (6.23), 353 (6.28), 327 (11.23), 210 (53.31), 192 (85.87), 191 (55.20), 180 (20.13), 178 (16.51), 177 (18.5), 167 (68.05), 154 (16.98), 149 (18.38); ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6); ^{13}C nmr (CDCl_3) data in Table 5.

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 386), m.p. 245–50 $^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 212, 232, 288, 327 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450, 1 700, 1 610, 1 580, 1 520, 1 500, 1 450 cm^{-1} ; MS 386 (M^+ , 100), 368 (95), 249 (40), 208 (90), 180 (80), 137 (85); ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6).

Source : *Aleurites moluccna* Hemsl.

Source : *Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br.

Hemidesminin-e (10)

Aleuritin (13)

$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 426), m.p. (amorphous), $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 219, 250, 324 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 430, 1 705, 1 615, 1 560, 1 510 cm^{-1} ; MS (426, M^+), 249 (100), 181 (95.5) and 178 (80); ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6).

$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_9$ (M^+ 416.1107), m.p. 238–39 $^\circ$ (MeOH); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 240, 320 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 470, 1 735, 1 620, 1 460, 1 229, 1 120, 1 040 and 820 cm^{-1} ; MS (416.1107, M^+), 398, 210, 208, 182, 167, 154; ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6); ^{13}C nmr (diacetate, CDCl_3) data in Table 5.

Source : *Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br

Source : *Aleurites fordii* Hemsl.

Hemidesmin-I (11)

Flacourtin (14)

$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_9$ (M^+ 416), m.p. 232–34 $^\circ$ (EtOAc-MeOH), $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, λ_{\max} (EtOH) 216, 232, 288, 320 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450, 1 700, 1 610, 1 580, 1 520, 1 500, 1 450 cm^{-1} ; MS 416 (M^+ , 4) 386 (17.69), 368 (16.73), 249 (6.21), 209 (59.75), 194 (24), 181 (97.51), 162 (26.29), 149 (34.89), 137 (100), 124 (90.63); ^1H nmr (DMSO- d_6).

Source : *Flacourtia sepiaria* Roxb.

Source : *Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br

Another technique for the structure elucidation of coumarino-lignoids has been developed through

TABLE 3-¹³C NMR DATA (ppm) OF CLEOMISCOSIN A (1), CLEOMISCOSIN B (2), CLEOMISCOSIN C (3), CLEOMISCOSIN D (4) AND THEIR DERIVATIVES*

	1 (C ₅ D ₅ N)	1a (CDCl ₃)	2 (C ₅ D ₅ N)	2a (CDCl ₃)	3 (C ₅ D ₅ N)	4 (C ₅ D ₅ N)	4a (CDCl ₃)
C-2	160.8s	160.4s	160.7s	160.4s	160.8s	160.7s	160.4s
C-3	113.6d	114.4d	113.8d	114.3d	113.7d	113.9d	114.4d
C-4	144.5d	143.5d	144.4d	143.5d	144.5d	144.4d	143.5d
C-5	101.1d	100.5d	101.2d	100.8d	101.0d	101.2d	100.8d
C-6	146.3s	145.8s	146.2s	145.7s	146.3s	146.3s	145.7s
C-7	138.4s	136.9s	138.1s	136.3s	138.1s	138.7s	136.3s
C-8	133.0s	131.7s	133.2s	132.1s	132.5s	133.8s	132.0s
C-9	139.3s	140.8s	139.4s	140.7s	139.2s	139.5s	138.8s
C-10	111.9s	111.9s	111.8s	111.8s	111.9s	111.8s	111.8s
C-1'	127.5s	133.5s	127.5s	133.5s	126.3s	126.5s	132.9s
C-2'	112.3d	111.5d	112.3d	111.3d	106.1d	106.6d	104.0d
C-3'	150.0s	151.7s	150.1s	151.6s	149.1s	150.2s	152.5s
C-4'	149.0s	138.8s	149.1s	138.8s	135.9s	135.1s	129.5s
C-5'	116.6d	123.3d	116.5d	123.2d	149.1s	150.2s	152.5s
C-6'	121.7d	119.9d	121.7d	119.8d	106.1d	106.6d	104.0d
C-7'	77.5d	76.7d	77.1d	76.0d	77.7d	77.5d	76.3d
C-8'	79.9d	75.1d	80.2d	75.6d	79.7d	80.2d	75.6d
C-9'	60.7t	62.4t	61.1t	62.4t	60.7t	61.1t	62.5t
OMe							56.4q
OMe	56.2q	56.0q	55.9q	56.0q	56.2q	56.1q	56.4q
OMe	55.8q	56.3q	56.1q	56.4q	56.4q	56.4q	
					56.4q	56.4q	
OAc		20.6q		20.6q			20.4q
		20.6q		20.6q			20.7q
		168.5s		168.6s			168.3s
		170.2s		170.2s			170.2s

* 1a = Cleomiscosin A - diacetate, 2a = cleomiscosin B-diacetate, 4a = cleomiscosin D-diacetate.

the application of the SINEPT pulse programme. Lin and Cordell²⁰ with the application of this technique have confirmed the assigned structures of cleomiscosin A(1) and B(2) and have been able to settle the structures of propacin (7) and aquillochin (8). The previously assigned structure of daphneticin (5) has been revised by employing this technique.

Biogenetically, cleomiscosin A and B may be obtained from the coumarin, fraxetin (15) and coniferyl alcohol (16) through a radical coupling as envisaged in case of xanthonolignoids, silybin and isosilybin²¹ (Chart 1).

In view of the interesting biological activities particularly cytotoxicity^{6,22} of coumarino-lignoids, a biomimetic synthesis has been achieved by Cordell and Lin⁸. They reported the synthesis of propacin (7) from fraxetin (15) and isoeugenol (17), aquillochin (8) from fraxetin and sinapyl alcohol (19), daphneticin (5) from daphnetin (18) and sinapyl alcohol by oxidative coupling. Oxidising agents like Ag₂O and DDQ were used for this purpose. However, enzymatic oxidation with horseradish peroxidase (Sigma) and chloroperoxidase (Sigma) gave better results and enzymatic oxidation was also found to be regioselective in most cases (Table 8).

TABLE 4-¹³C NMR DATA (ppm) OF DAPHNETICIN (5) AND DAPHNETICIN DIACETATE

	Daphneticin (C ₅ D ₅ N)	Daphneticin diacetate (CDCl ₃)
C-2	160.4s	160.2s
C-3	113.6d	113.9d
C-4	144.3d	143.8d
C-5	119.8d	119.9d
C-6	113.2d	113.9d
C-7	147.6s	146.5s
C-8	138.4s	133.3s
C-9	149.2s	150.6s
C-10	113.6s	113.7s
C-1''	126.4s	131.7s
C-2''	106.3d	104.0d
C-3''	149.2d	152.8s
C-4''	132.2s	123.3s
C-5''	149.2s	152.8s
C-6''	106.3d	104.0d
C-1'	77.8d	77.2d
C-2'	79.9d	75.5d
C-3'	60.7*t	62.7t
OMe x 2	56.4q	56.3q

*168.5s, 170.2s, 20.5q and 20.6q for two CoMe.

TABLE 5-¹³C NMR DATA (ppm) OF MOLUCCANIN (10) DIACETATE AND ALLURITIN (13) DIACETATE

	Moluccanin diacetate (CDCl ₃)	Aleuritin diacetate (CDCl ₃)
C-2	160.92dd	161.21
C-3	114.45d	112.32
C-4	142.70dd	137.64
C-5	114.30d	139.50
C-6	139.90s	128.90
C-7	146.7m	152.30
C-8	105.04d	93.33
C-9	149.30m	149.60
C-10	113.20m	103.30
C-1'	132.90s	133.00
C-2'	103.70dq	104.00
C-3'	152.1brs	152.74
C-4'	129.50s	129.10
C-5'	152.1brs	152.74
C-6'	103.70dq	104.00
C-7'		77.40
C-8'	77.20brd	75.23
C-9'	62.30t	62.59
OMeX2	56.10q	56.60, 56.31
OAc	170.1s (9')	168.36, 170.22
OAc	168.2s (4')	
Me	20.50q (9)	20.39, 20.62
	20.30q (4)	

TABLE 6-DECOUPLING EXPERIMENTS ON 13

Irradiated at	Effect at δ			
	5.01	4.279	4.42	4.11
5.01	-	p→q	NE	NE
4.279	d→s	-	dd→d	dd→d
4.42	NE	p→q	-	-

NE = no effect.

TABLE 7-NOE (%) AND CHEMICAL SHIFT OBSERVED FOR 13-DIACETATE

Irradiated signal (δ)	Observed signals			
	H-3	H-4	H-8	OMe
3.96	-	-	6.55	-
7.92	6.23 (18.75)	-	(26.66)	-
6.55	-	-	-	3.96 (10.0)

* Increase in signal heights is shown in parenthesis.

Chart 1

- (15) R¹ = OMe, R² = OH
 (16) R¹ = CH₂OH, R² = H
 (18) R¹ = H, R² = OH
 (17) R¹ = Me, R² = H
 (20) R¹ = OH, R² = H
 (19) R¹ = CH₂OH, R² = OMe

(21)

TABLE 8—SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINO-LIGNOIDS

Coumarin	Phenylpropene	Oxidising agent	Condition	Yield of isomeric coumarino-lignoids (%)
Fraxetin (15)	Coniferyl alcohol (16)	Ag ₂ O	20 h, r.t.	10.4 : 6.5 [(1) : (2)]
(15)	(16)	HRP	1 week, 37°	22.6 : 2.7 [(1) : (2)]
(15)	Isoeugenol (17)	Ag ₂ O	20 h, r.t.	4.1 : 2.6 [(7) : (21)]
(15)	(17)	DDQ	28 h, r.t.	10.8 [(7) : (21)]
(15)	(17)	HRP	1 week, 37°	29.0 :- [(7) : (21)]
(15)	(17)	HRP-H ₂ O ₂	2 week, 37°	87.2 :- [(7) : (21)]
(15)	Sinapyl alcohol(19)	Ag ₂ O	18 h, r.t.	6.8 : 6.2 [(8) : (4)]
(15)	(19)	HRP	2 week, 37°	17.5 : 0.5 [(8) : (4)]
Aesculetin (20)	(17)	Ag ₂ O	6 h, r.t.	8.4 : 1.1
(20)	(17)	DDQ	24 h, r.t.	2.4 :-
(20)	(17)	HRP	2 week, 37°	8.3 :-
(20)	(17)	CP	3 week, 37°	4.6 :-
(20)	(16)	Ag ₂ O	20 h, r.t.	1.9 : 0.8
(20)	(16)	HRP	2 week, 37°	7.9 :-
Daphetin (18)	(17)	Ag ₂ O	24 h, r.t.	5.0 : 1.3
(18)	(17)	HRP	2 week, 37°	19 :-
(18)	(19)	Ag ₂ O	24 h, r.t.	1.0 :- [(5)]
(18)	(19)	HRP	19 day, 37°	5.8 :- [(5)]

The spectral data (uv, ir and nmr) of the products clearly indicated that they were *trans*-substituted coumarino-lignoids. However, the distinction between the two regioisomers was not always possible.

HRP = Horseradish peroxidase, CP = Chloroperoxidase.

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